

Cooperative Low-Complexity Base Station Management in Millimeter Wave Heterogeneous Networks

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Abstract—In this paper, we study the problem of base station (BS) cooperation in millimeter wave multi-tier heterogeneous cellular networks. In contrast to conventional approaches, where a number of BSs jointly transmit data to a user, we investigate a low-complexity technique that enables the selection of a single BS for transmission. Specifically, a single BS that provides the highest instantaneous signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio is selected, among the strongest BSs from each tier. By using stochastic geometry tools, we derive closed-form expressions for the coverage probability and the diversity gain of the system by taking into account spatial randomness and blockage effects. Our results show that the proposed scheme achieves full diversity and is appropriate for networks with strict computation constraints. In addition, we study the case where users employ successive interference cancellation (SIC) to further boost the achieved performance; SIC allows the mitigation of strong interference terms from the received signal. The impact of SIC on the coverage probability of the system is studied and closed-form expressions are provided.

1. INTRODUCTION

The wireless industry is currently facing the barrier of limited available spectrum for commercial cellular systems and an increasing demand for data traffic. To address this demand, one of the solutions is ultra-densification that forms smallcell networks, i.e., macro-, pico-cell or relay nodes that can increase area spectral efficiency. The network densification, along with the implementation of millimeter wave (mmWave) bands (10-300 GHz), can enable Gb/s-level access speeds with less spectrum usage and lower power consumption [1]. The need to mitigate mmWave high path losses is fulfilled by the implementation of directional antennas with high

power gains [2]. On the other hand, the additional interference caused by the network densification, shifts the research community's interest towards the study of effective interference management schemes and interference mitigation techniques to achieve successful communication and better network performance [3].

An efficient technique for increasing the network performance is the cooperation among interconnected distributed base stations (BSs). The authors in [4], investigate a noncoherent joint transmission BS cooperative scheme and characterize the performance from a system-level standpoint. In [5], a low-complexity BS cooperation technique is proposed for high frequency networks and the performance is evaluated for scenarios with channel state information (CSI) at the transmitter. In [6], a heterogeneous cellular network where each user is served by a number of nearby single-antenna BSs to mitigate inter-cell interference is considered. The work in [7] studies the negative effects of blockages/obstacles and analyzes the coverage performance for cellular networks. In [8], the authors study a BS cooperative technique for mmWave heterogeneous networks with multi-user precoding. Another technique for improving the network performance is the employment of directional antennas that provide high link gains. The authors in [9] show that directional antennas reduce the received interference and support higher densities and larger spectral efficiencies. The authors in [10] study mmWave cellular networks and show that beamforming can provide significant gains. On the other hand, the need for better network performance has motivated the study of more sophisticated techniques for multi-user interference mitigation. As such, the successive interference cancellation (SIC) scheme is investigated in [11], where the authors evaluate the performance after successfully decoding and canceling the most dominant interfering signals. Further study of SIC in heterogeneous networks with arbitrary propagation effects is studied in [12].

In this paper, we study the downlink performance of a heterogeneous mmWave cellular network with BS cooperation. We adopt a system level point of view by taking into account both BS and blockage spatial randomness. The main contribution of this paper is the development of a low-complexity BS cooperation scheme, where a single BS is selected among the strongest BSs from each tier. The proposed BS cooperation scheme is attractive for practical and low complexity implementations. We develop closed-form expressions

for the coverage probability and the diversity gain of the system, when CSI is available at the BSs and antenna directionality is employed. Our results show the impact of blockages on the achieved performance and reveal that the proposed scheme provides full diversity gain. In addition, we study a SIC scheme for the downlink in order to further improve the achieved performance through mitigation of dominant interferers. Closed-form expressions for the coverage probability are also provided for the scenarios with SIC deployment.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we present the system model and the main assumptions of the paper. In Section III, we introduce our proposed lowcomplexity BS cooperative scheme and the derived analytical results. Simulation results are presented in Section IV, followed by our conclusions in Section V.

Notation: \mathbb{R}^d denotes the d -dimensional Euclidean space; $P[X]$ denotes the probability of the event X and $E[X]$ represents the expected value of X .

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a heterogeneous mmWave cellular network composed by K independent tiers of BSs. Each network tier is modeled by a two-dimensional homogeneous Poisson point process (PPP) $\Phi_k = \{x_k \in \mathbb{R}^2\}$ with density λ_k and all BSs belonging in tier k , $1 \leq k \leq K$, transmit with the same power P_k . We assume the existence of an ideal backhaul network that connects the BSs and provides the ability (to BSs from different network tiers) to cooperate and jointly transmit data to a user [6]. Fig. 1 schematically presents the system model. A single directional antenna is assumed to be employed at each terminal (BSs and users) and is modeled as in [9]. Specifically, antenna arrays are modeled as a sectorized antenna model and the gain of the link between the receiver and a transmitting BS located at x is given by $G_x = \{MM, Mm, mm\}$, with the corresponding probabilities $p_{G_x} = \left\{ \left(\frac{\theta}{\pi}\right)^2, 2\frac{\theta(\pi-\theta)}{\pi^2}, \left(\frac{\pi-\theta}{\pi}\right)^2 \right\}$. Let θ denote the beamwidth of the main lobe, M and m the main and the side lobe gain, respectively. Furthermore, we assume the active link between each user and its associated BS lies in the boresight direction of the antennas of both terminals, resulting in a link gain MM , which is denoted by G_o . We assume the blockages are modeled by a line segment process of two dimensional lines with random lengths and orientations [7]. As such, the path-loss exponent of a BS with link distance d

from the user is a discrete random variable $a(d)$. The value of variable $a(d)$ depends on whether the communication link is unobstructed or not. Specifically,

variable $a(d)$ takes the value a_L , when the link is line-of-sight (LOS) with probability $P[LOS] = \exp(-\beta d)$ and a_N , when is non-LOS (NLOS) with probability $1 - P[LOS]$. The non-negative blockage constant, β , depends on the density and length of the blockages. Without loss of generality and by following Slivnyak's theorem [14], we study the coverage probability of a user located at the origin.

Let the set of locations of the BSs, which have the desired transmit signal X , be denoted by $\mathcal{C} \subset \cup_{k=1}^K \Phi_k$ and of the active interfering BSs by $\mathcal{Y} \subset \cup_{k=1}^K \Phi_k \setminus \mathcal{C}$. We assume that each user attempts to connect with the BS that provides the maximum average power [6]. Thus, we

define the set of candidate BSs as
$$\mathcal{C} = \left\{ (x_{(0,1)}, \dots, x_{(0,K)}) : x_{(0,k)} = \arg \max_{x \in \Phi_k} \frac{P_{\nu(x_k)}}{\|x_k\|^{-a(x_k)}} \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where $x_{(0,k)}$ is the location of the strongest BS from tier k . The low computational demand of the technique proposed follows from the assumption that a controller in the backhaul network implements a low-complexity BS selection (BSS) scheme and is based on the concept of antennas selection [13]. The BSS

Fig. 1. The network model; a user receives the useful signal from the selected BS (solid blue line) and faces interfering signals from active LOS BSs (dashed red lines) and active NLOS BSs (dotted red lines). The solid black lines represent the blockages.

scheme chooses the BS that provides the maximum signal-tointerference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) to the user from the set

\mathcal{C} i.e., the BS at $x_o = \max(x_{(0,1)}, \dots, x_{(0,K)})$. Therefore, the received channel output can be written as

$$Y = \frac{G_o^{1/2} P_{\nu(x_o)}^{1/2}}{\|x_o\|^{a(x_o)/2}} |h_{x_o}| X + \sum_{x \in \mathcal{Y}} \frac{G_x^{1/2} P_{\nu(x)}^{1/2}}{\|x\|^{a(x)/2}} |h_x| X_x + Z, \quad (2)$$

where h_x denotes the fading coefficient between the transmitter at x and the user, which is assumed to be Rayleigh fading with unit variance; h_x are assumed to be independent and identically distributed. Furthermore, X_x denotes the transmitted signal from the interfering BSs; $v(x)$ is the index of the network tier to which the BS located at $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$ belongs i.e., $v(x) = k$ if and only if $x \in \Phi_k$; and finally, $Z \sim \text{CN}(\mathbf{o}, \sigma^2)$ denotes the thermal noise at the user, which is a standard additive circular complex white Gaussian random variable with variance σ^2 .

We assume that each user implements an ideal SIC based on the proposed technique in [12]. The main idea of SIC is to decode the dominant interference signals and subtract them from the incoming signal, resulting in an increase of the observed SINR. The number of interferers that can be canceled is assumed to be limited to $n \in \mathbb{N}$ in order to keep both the computational complexity and power consumption at low levels. The user attempts to decode the received signal from the BS, which has been selected by the BSS scheme. If this attempt is unsuccessful, the user seeks to decode the dominant interference signal, subtract it from the incoming signal, and then re-attempt to decode the resulting received signal. This is repeated up to n times, until the received signal is decoded. The received signals at the user from all BSs regardless of the network tier, can be ordered as $\{X_{(1)}, X_{(2)}, \dots\}$ such that $X_{(i)} \geq X_{(j)}$ with $i \leq j$ and

$$X_{(i)} = G_{xi} P_{v(x_i)} |h_{xi}|^2 ||x_{(i)}||^{-a(x_{(i)})}.$$

We evaluate the network's performance using the coverage probability $P(T)$, that is the probability that the SINR is greater than a given threshold T i.e., $P(T) = P[\text{SINR} > T]$. Denote by SINR_{\max} the maximum SINR provided by the BS which is selected by the BSS scheme. Therefore, with uncorrelated branches, the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of SINR_{\max} is

$$P[\text{SINR}_{\max} < T] = \prod_{i=1}^K (1 - P_i(T)), \tag{3}$$

where $P_i(T)$ denotes the instantaneous coverage probability from the strongest BS of tier i .

III. BS SELECTION SCHEME AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In this section, we analytically derive the coverage probability and diversity order of a downlink cellular network, which implements our proposed technique. The instantaneous SINR from the BS of tier i , can be written as

$$\text{SINR}_i = \frac{G_0 P_i ||x_{(0,i)}||^{-a(x_{(0,i)})} |h_{x_{(0,i)}}|^2}{I_\Phi + \sigma^2}, \tag{4}$$

where $I_\Phi = P_{y \in Y} G_y P_{v(y)} |h_y|^2 ||y||^{-a(y)}$ denotes the aggregate interference power due to the non-cooperative BSs in tier $v(y)$. We first derive the diversity order of our proposed technique. In this case, the diversity is defined as the rate of convergence of the outage probability to zero in the high SINR regime, i.e., $T \rightarrow \infty$ [6]. Hence, it can be expressed as

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log(P[\text{SINR}_{\max} < T])}{\log T}. \tag{5}$$

We show that our low-complexity technique provides full diversity gain and follows asymptotically the behavior of advanced cooperation techniques with jointly BS transmission. Following similar steps as in [6], we present the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *The diversity order of the proposed BS selection technique for $K > 1$, is equal to K .*

Proof. The numerator of (4) is an independent Rayleigh distributed random variable with probability density function $\frac{x}{S_i^2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2S_i^2}\right)$, $x \geq 0$ with $S_i = G_0^{1/2} P_i^{1/2} ||x_{(0,i)}||^{-a(x_{(0,i)})/2}$, $x_{(0,i)} \in \mathcal{C}$. By letting $I = I_\Phi + \sigma^2$, the outage probability is given by

$$P[\text{SINR}_{\max} < T] = \prod_{i=1}^K P(\text{SINR}_i < T) \tag{6}$$

$$= \prod_{i=1}^K \left(P\left(G_0 P_i ||x_{(0,i)}||^{-a(x_{(0,i)})} |h_{x_{(0,i)}}|^2 < TI \right) \right) \tag{7}$$

$$= \prod_{i=1}^K \left(\mathbb{E}_{S_i, I} \left[\int_0^{\sqrt{TI}} \frac{x_{(0,i)}}{S_i^2} \exp\left(-\frac{x_{(0,i)}^2}{2S_i^2}\right) dx_{(0,i)} \right] \right) \tag{8}$$

$$= T^K \prod_{i=1}^K \mathbb{E}_{S_i, I} \left[I \int_0^1 \frac{z_i}{S_i^2} \exp\left(-\frac{TI z_i^2}{2S_i^2}\right) dz_i \right], \tag{9}$$

where (9) follows from the change of variable $x_{(0,i)} = \sqrt{TI} z_i$. At the high coverage regime i.e., $T \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$I \int_0^1 \frac{z_i}{S_i^2} \exp\left(-\frac{TI z_i^2}{2S_i^2}\right) dz_i \sim I \int_0^1 \frac{z_i}{S_i^2} dz_i. \tag{10}$$

As a result,

$$P[\text{SINR}_{\max} < T] \approx T^K \prod_{i=1}^K \mathbb{E}_{S_i, I} \left[I \int_0^1 \frac{z_i}{S_i^2} dz_i \right]. \tag{11}$$

Substituting (11) in (5), the diversity gain is

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\log T^K}{\log T} + \frac{\log \left(\prod_{i=1}^K \mathbb{E}_{S_i, I} \left[I \int_0^1 \frac{z_i}{S_i^2} dz_i \right] \right)}{\log T} \right) \stackrel{(a)}{=} K, \tag{12}$$

where (a) is due to the fact that the second term of the equation for $T \rightarrow 0$ converges to zero. \square

We now proceed to the analysis of the coverage probability of the heterogeneous mmWave cellular network considered.

Let $\Gamma_i = \left\{ \frac{\|x\|^a}{P_i}, x \in \Phi_i \right\}$ denote the normalised path-loss between each BS in Φ_i and the user and let $\gamma_k = \frac{\|x_k\|^a}{P_{\nu(k)}}$ the normalized path-loss between the user and a BS belonging to tier k . The strongest BS from network tier i with distance $x_{(0,i)}$, it has a normalized path loss given by $\gamma_{(0,i)}$. Let $\gamma = (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_K)$, then using the mapping theorem [14], Γ_i is a PPP with density function $\lambda(\gamma)$ and joint distribution $f_{\Gamma}(\gamma)$ which are given in [8, Appendix A].

A. BS selection with sectorized antennas

In what follows, we present the analytical results for the BS cooperation scheme described in Section II.

Theorem 1. *The coverage probability of a downlink user in a heterogeneous network with sectorized antennas and with the existence of blockages is given by*

$$\mathcal{P}(T) = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^K \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^K \int_0^{\infty} \exp(-s\sigma^2) \mathcal{L}_{I_{\Gamma_k}}(s) f_{\Gamma}(\gamma) d\gamma \right) \tag{13}$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_{I_{\Gamma_k}}(s) = \exp \left(- \sum_t p_t \int_{\gamma_k}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{1 + s^{-1} u t^{-1}} \right) \lambda(u) du \right), \tag{14}$$

with $t \in \{MM, Mm, mm\}$ and $s = \frac{T\gamma_{(0,i)}}{2G_0}$.

Proof. See Appendix. \square

The derived expression in (13) provides a general result for the coverage probability of mmWave cellular networks with sectorized antennas. In order to further gain insights on the behaviour of the network and simplify the above expressions, we investigate the case of high blockage density, i.e., we study the asymptotic case with $\beta \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\mathcal{P}_s(j, k) = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^K \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^K \int_{c(j,k)}^{\infty} \exp \left(- \sum_t p_t \int_{c(j,k)}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{2uG_0}{T\gamma_i t}} \right) \lambda(u) du \right) f_{\Gamma}(\gamma) d\gamma \right). \tag{18}$$

This case provides the lower bound for the coverage probability due to the absence of unobstructed links between users and BSs i.e., $P[LOS] = 0$ and $P[NLOS] = 1$. To further simplify the derived theoretical expressions, we set $a_N = 4$ that corresponds to an urban propagation environment [8]; as a result (14) is simplified to

$$\mathcal{L}_{I_{\Gamma_k}}(s) = \exp \left(- \sum_t p_t \pi \lambda_k \sqrt{\frac{P_k t}{s}} \arctan \left[\sqrt{\frac{s}{t \gamma_k}} \right] \right), \tag{15}$$

and the joint distribution is simplified to

$$f_{\Gamma}(\gamma) = \prod_{i=1}^K \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{2P_k^{\frac{2}{a_N}} \pi \gamma_i^{\frac{2}{a_N}-1} \lambda_k}{a_N} e^{-\sum_{k=1}^K \pi \lambda_k (\gamma_k P_k)^{\frac{2}{a_N}}}. \tag{16}$$

B. Interference cancellation with BS selection

In this section, we study the performance of our proposed technique by further assuming that the users employ the SIC scheme. Firstly, we study the success probability of the user after canceling the strongest interferers and with the assumption that the interfering power of noise is negligible. The area around the user, which is free of interfering BSs in the network tier k after canceling j interferers, can be approximated as a circle

with radius $R_{j,k} = \sqrt{\frac{j}{\lambda_k \pi}}$ [12]. Since the cell association policy is the averaged received power, we have

$c(j, k) = \frac{P_{j,k}^{\alpha(x_k)}}{P_{\nu(x_k)}}$ which provides the cancellation radius in tier k after cancelling j interfering BSs based on the average received power. Given that j strongest interferers have been canceled, the coverage probability of the user is given by,

$$\mathcal{P}_s(j, k) = \mathbb{P} \left[|h_{x_0}|^2 G_0 P_{\nu(x_0)} \|x_0\|^{-a(x_0)} > \frac{T}{I_{\Omega_j}} \right], \tag{17}$$

where I_{Ω_j} is the set of interferers after cancelling j interferers. We can now derive the following lemma.

Lemma 2. *Given that j strongest equivalent interferers have been canceled, the successful transmission probability of the user is given by (18).*

Proof. The proof follows similar steps as the proof of Theorem 1. The main difference is that the SIC scheme eliminates j interfering BSs and so the remaining interfering BSs in tier k appear outside of a circle with

radius $c(j,k)$. A detailed proof is omitted due to space limitations. \square

We now derive the success probability of a user to decode and cancel the j -th strongest signal [12], with the idealistic assumption that the interference for the $j-1$ strongest signals has been previously canceled.

Lemma 3. The success probability of decoding the j -th strongest signal of the user that successfully canceled the $j-1$ strongest signal is given by (19).

Proof. After canceling $j-1$ interferers, the success probability of decoding the j -th strongest signal, can be derived again using similar steps as the proof of Theorem 1. In this case, the distance to the j -th strongest BS in tier k is $\left[\frac{R_{j,k}^{\alpha(x_k)}}{P_{\nu(x_k)}} \right]$. The proof is omitted due to space limitations. \square

We now present the main theorem for the coverage probability by also taking into account the SIC scheme.

Theorem 2. The coverage probability P_{SIC} of a downlink user that applies SIC to cancel a maximum of n interferers is given by

$$P_{SIC}(T) = P(T) \prod_{i=1}^n \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} P_d(T, j) P_s(j, k), \quad (20)$$

where $P_s(j, k)$ and $P_d(T, j)$ are given by (18) and (19), respectively.

Proof. The proof follows from the definition of the sequence of events given in Section II and Lemmas 2 and 3. \square

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we provide numerical results to verify our model and illustrate the effectiveness and potential benefits of the proposed BS selection scheme. We focus on the special case of a heterogeneous network with $K = 2$ tiers i.e., consisting of a macro-tier overlaid with a pico-tier. We assume that the BS density of the first and second tier is $\lambda_1 = 5 \times 10^{-5}$ and $\lambda_2 = 3\lambda_1$, respectively; the transmit power for each network tier is $P_1 = 30$ dB and $P_2 = 50$ dB, respectively. Furthermore, we assume that the non-negative blockage constant is $\beta = 0.008$. The noise power is set to $\sigma^2 = -70$ dB and the path loss exponent of a LOS and a NLOS link is set to $a_L = 2$ and $a_N = 4$, respectively. The parameters for the sectorized antenna model are set to $M = 10$ for the main lobe gain, $m = 0.1$ for side lobe gain and $\theta = \frac{\pi}{6}$ for the main lobe beamwidth [9].

Fig. 2 illustrates the effects of blockage/obstacles on the mmWave network performance. The first main observation is the negative effect of the blockages on the coverage probability. This observation was expected,

since as the density of blockages increases, the number of blocked links between the users and the associated BSs also increases. By decreasing the probability of LOS connection, the signal at the user side becomes weaker and the received SINR is reduced. Moreover, for the case with BS cooperation and antenna sectorization (scenario ‘‘CS’’), it can be easily observed the significant performance improvement against a conventional network with omnidirectional antennas (scenario ‘‘OM’’), independently on the blockage constant values i.e., for $T = 0$ dB, it achieves

$$P_d(T, j) = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^K \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^K \int_0^\infty \exp \left(- \sum_t p_t \int_{c(j,k)} \left(\frac{1}{1} \right) \right) \right)$$

Fig. 2. Coverage probability versus the threshold t for different values of blockage constant; $M = 1$.

about 50% increase. In addition, with the elimination of the dominant interfering BS ($n = 1$) (scenario ‘‘CSS’’), we can observe a further improvement on the coverage performance at low to moderate SINR thresholds. Finally, the figure shows that the analytical expressions (13) and (20), which are represented by dashed lines, perfectly match the simulation results and validate our theoretical derivations.

Fig. 3 shows the impact of the proposed BS selection on the coverage performance for different blockage constants. As it can be seen, the coverage performance improves with K due to the additional transmit diversity gain. Specifically, the probability that a user communicates with a stronger BS increases with respect to network tier number. As the number of network tier increases, the number of associated BSs with the users increases, providing an increased probability to

communicate with a stronger BS. This results in an improvement of observed SINR i.e., 35% improvement for $T = 20$ dB and $K = 3$ compared with the case $K = 2$. Furthermore, the network performance decreases with the increase of the blockage constant, independently on the number of network tiers K . The worst coverage performance refers to the scenario where the entire links between the user and the BSs are blocked, i.e., when $\beta \rightarrow \infty$. The network performance for this scenario is given by using (15) and corresponds to a lower bound of the network's performance.

Finally, Fig. 4 reveals the impact of blockage density on the network performance for different sectorized antenna configurations. It is interesting to note that at low blockage constant values, the existence of blockages improves the network per-

Fig. 3. Coverage probability versus the threshold T for different values of blockage constant; $\lambda_3 = 5 \times \lambda_1$ and $P_3 = 80$ dB.

formance. However, by increasing the blockage constant beyond a critical point, the network performance decreases. This observation is based on the fact that at low blockage constants, the interfering signals from LOS BSs are blocked, while the users are still able to communicate with strong LOS BSs. In contrast, for high blockage densities, the communication of the users with LOS BSs becomes impossible and thus the coverage probability significantly decreases. In addition, by narrowing the antenna's main lobe beamwidth, the coverage performance increases. This observation was expected, since by narrowing the main lobe beamwidth, the multi-user interference from interfering BSs is reduced and the observed SINR increases. Finally, it is clear that as the blockage density increases, the network performance converges to the lower bound ($\beta \rightarrow \infty$), which is based on (15).

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have dealt with the BS cooperation in heterogeneous multi-tier mmWave cellular networks. A low complexity BS selection scheme, where a single BS is selected among the strongest BSs from each tier has been investigated. We have shown that the proposed BS selection ensures full diversity gain with lower computational demands compared to the conventional approaches. Analytical expressions for the coverage probability have been derived and the impact of blockage density, antenna directionality and number of network tiers has been discussed. In order to further boost the achieved performance, a SIC mechanism has been

integrated at the user's side to mitigate strong interference terms. A future

Fig. 4. Coverage probability versus blockage constant for different antennas beamwidth; $T = 0$ dB.

extension of this work is the consideration of a distance-based power control to handle the effects of multi-user interference.

APPENDIX

The instantaneous coverage probability $P_i(T)$ from the strongest BS of tier i , denoted by $x_{0,i}$, in a downlink mmWave heterogeneous network with K tiers is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_i(T) &= \mathbb{P}[\text{SINR}_i > T] \\
 &= \mathbb{P} \left[|h_{x_{(0,i)}}|^2 > \frac{T \|x_{(0,i)}\|^{a(x_{(0,i)})}}{P_i G_0} (\sigma^2 + I_\Phi) \right] \\
 &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \mathbb{E}_{\gamma, I_\Gamma} \left[\exp \left(-\frac{T(\sigma^2 + I_\Gamma)}{2G_0 \gamma_{(0,i)}^{-1}} \right) \right] \\
 &\stackrel{(b)}{=} \mathbb{E}_\gamma \left[\mathcal{L}_{I_\Gamma} \left(\frac{T}{2G_0 \gamma_{(0,i)}^{-1}} \right) \exp \left(-\frac{T\sigma^2}{2G_0 \gamma_{(0,i)}^{-1}} \right) \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows from the fact that $|h_{x_{(0,i)}}|^2$ is a Rayleigh random variable, hence $P_i G_0 |h_{x_{(0,i)}}|^2 x_{(0,i)}^{-a(x_{(0,i)})}$ is exponentially distributed with mean $2P_i G_0 x_{(0,i)}^{-a(x_{(0,i)})}$. In (b), we make use of the Laplace transform of I_Γ , where $\mathcal{L}_\Gamma(s) = \mathbb{E}[\exp(-sI_\Gamma)]$. Then, by setting $s = \frac{T\gamma_{(0,i)}}{2G_0}$, the instantaneous coverage probability is given by

$$P_i(T) = \int_{\gamma_{(0,i)}=0}^{\infty} e^{-s\sigma^2} \mathcal{L}_{I_\Gamma}(s) f_\Gamma(\gamma_{(0,i)}) d\gamma_{(0,i)}. \quad (21)$$

The mutual independence of the PPPs Γ_k , implies the independence of I_{Γ_k} . Furthermore, due to the independence between the antenna link gains, the interference I_{Γ_k} can be handled as three independent PPPs for network tier k , such that $I_{\Gamma_k} =$

$I_{\Gamma_k}^{(MM)} + I_{\Gamma_k}^{(Mm)} + I_{\Gamma_k}^{(mm)}$. Essentially, each expectation is a Laplace transform, i.e. $\mathcal{L}_{I_{\Gamma_k}^{(G_\gamma)}}(s) = \mathbb{E}_{\Gamma_k} \left[\exp \left(-s I_{\Gamma_k}^{(G_\gamma)} \right) \right]$ of the associated sub-PPP, and these Laplace transforms are multiplied together to obtain the Laplace transform for I_{Γ_k} , that is $\mathcal{L}_{I_{\Gamma_k}}(s) = \prod_t \mathcal{L}_{I_{\Gamma_k}^{(t)}}(s)$. Therefore, we can evaluate each as follows,

$$\mathcal{L}_{I_{\Gamma_k}^{(G_\gamma)}}(s) \stackrel{(a)}{=} \mathbb{E}_{\Gamma_k, |h_\gamma|^2} \left[\exp \left(-s \sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma_k \setminus \gamma_k} |h_\gamma|^2 \gamma^{-1} G_\gamma \right) \right] \quad (22)$$

$$= \mathbb{E}_{\Gamma_k} \left[\prod_{\gamma \in \Gamma_k \setminus \gamma(0,k)} \mathbb{E}_{|h_\gamma|^2} \left[\exp \left(-s |h_\gamma|^2 \gamma^{-1} G_\gamma \right) \right] \right] \quad (23)$$

$$\stackrel{(b)}{=} \exp \left(-p_{G_\gamma} \int_{u > \gamma(0,k)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + su^{-1} G_\gamma} \right) \lambda(u) du \right), \quad (24)$$

where (a) uses the definition of $I_{\Gamma_k}^{(G_\gamma)}$; (b) follows from the moment generating function of an exponential random variable and due to the probability generating functional of a PPP. Hence, by multiplying the Laplace transforms for the different cases of antenna gains, we have (14) and the result follows.

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